

Antibacterial activity and Phytochemical screening of the Acetone Extract of the root of *Aloe vera* (L.) Burm. F. against microorganisms associated with Male Infertility

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ABSTRACT

The phytochemical screening and antibacterial activity of the acetone root extract of *Aloe vera* was investigated in this study. Different concentrations (200 mg/ml, 100 mg/ml and 50 mg/ml) were prepared and tested against seven different bacterial isolates which included *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Staphylococcus saprophyticus* and *Proteus mirabilis*. Phytochemical screening of the acetone root extract was done using standard test procedures. Susceptibility testing was done by employing the agar diffusion technique while the microtitre plate method was used for the minimum inhibitory concentration.. The phytochemical screening revealed a high presence of carbohydrates and slight presence of glycosides, alkaloids and saponins. The antimicrobial attribute of the extract indicated highest activity at 200 mg/ml against *Streptococcus pyogenes* with an inhibitory zone of 22.00 mm while the lowest activity was observed at 50 mg/ml against *Proteus mirabilis* with zone of inhibition of 5.33mm. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) as low as 6.25mg/ml was achieved against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus pyogenes*. It is concluded that the phytoconstituents of *Aloe vera* root were of medicinal importance and had the ability to successfully inhibit the growth of microorganisms which are of significant health concerns to mankind. Thus the plant is probably a suitable choice for the development of new drugs that could be used to treat some ailments which afflict man.

INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants have played an important role in the traditional and orthodox system of medicine in the curing of different types of diseases (Yeboella *et al.*, 2011). Analysis of different species of medicinal plants for biologically active components known to have pharmacological properties have been investigated and most of the plants have shown antimicrobial property (Rabe and Van Staden, 1997; Ongsakul *et al.*, 2009; Ahsan *et al.*, 2009). Today, the World Health Organization estimates that up to 80 percent of people still rely mainly on traditional medicines particularly from plants. This brings to fore the need for the development of scientific technology for the enhancement of medicinal plants and their products (Mukherjee and Wahile, 2006). In fact, many of the current drugs either mimic naturally occurring molecules or have structures that are fully or in part derived from natural sources (Baby and Raj, 2010). Natural antimicrobials can be derived from barks, stems, leaves, flowers and fruits of plants, various animal tissues or from microorganisms (Klein and Penneys, 1988).

Alove vera (L.) also called *Aloe barbadensis* is one medicinal plant that has been reported to have a myriad of therapeutic properties. It is an ancient plant that have been said to have legendary medicinal reputation dating back to thousands of years ago (Asma *et al.*, 2011). Since biblical times, aloe plants have figured among folkloric remedies as purgatives and as treatments for skin disorders. It is commonly called aloe, burn plant, lily of the desert and elephant's gall (Baby and Raj, 2010). Aloes have long been in use for several diseases, particularly connected with the digestive system; they have also been used for wounds, burns and skin problems (Rajeshwari *et al.*, 2012). The root was ethnomedically reported by Erhabor, *et al.* (2013) to have the potential to treat low libido. Available literatures (Paulsen *et al.*, 2005; Belo *et al.*, 2006; Asma *et al.*, 2011; Bashir *et al.*, 2011; Rajeshwari *et al.*, 2012) revealed that the antimicrobial properties of various extracts of different parts of *Aloe vera* abound and have been tested against pathogenic and non-pathogenic organisms. However, there is a paucity of scientific work on the antimicrobial potential of the root. It is against this back drop that the acetone extract of the root of the plant was investigated for its antibacterial property against organisms isolated from semen. The qualitative chemical constituents of acetone extract of the plant was also determined.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection and extraction of plant material

Fresh roots of *Aloe vera* plant were harvested thoroughly rinsed with water and air dried at room temperature. The dried root pieces was blended to powder using a mechanical grinder. The powdered samples (195.0 g) of the pulverized root was introduced into an air tight extraction tank. 2.5L of acetone was added to the extraction tank with steady agitation and was allowed to stand for proper maceration. After 48 hours, the acetone extract was filtered and the filtrate collected and concentrated by evaporation in a water bath at 45°C. The yield was weighed and the extract kept in a refrigerator at 4°C prior to antimicrobial sensitivity test. The percentage yield of the extract was appropriately determined using the formular ($\% \text{ yield of extract} = \text{Weight of extract after maceration (g)} / \text{weight of powdered root (g)} \times 100/1$). For the preparation of varying concentrations of the extract for antibacterial assay, the extract was reconstituted to obtain 200mg/ml, 100 mg/ml and 50 mg/ml concentrations. These were obtained by dissolving 2 g, 1g and 0.1g of the extract in 1ml of dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) in different test tubes. These were then transferred into test tubes containing 9ml of distilled water. The reconstituted extract were then stored in sample bottles until required.

Phytochemical Screening

The root extract was subjected to phytochemical tests using methods as described by Trease and Evans (1983) to test for alkaloids, flavonoids, steroids, terpenoids, saponins, cardiac glycosides and carbohydrates.

Collection of seminal fluid specimen

The sperm specimens were collected from male patients attending University of Benin Teaching Hospital (UBTH) and St. Philomena Hospital, Benin City, Edo State. The sperm specimens were collected into sterile universal bottles and transported immediately to the laboratory at a temperature close to that of the human body.

Isolation, identification and standardization of bacterial isolates The sperm specimen was streaked onto Nutrient agar for isolation of non-fastidious bacteria. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24-48 hours. After incubation, the bacterial species were identified by Gram staining and biochemical tests following standard procedures

outlined by Cheesbrough, (2000). In standardizing the isolates, a loopful of the stock culture of the organisms was inoculated into 5 ml sterile nutrient broth and incubated for 24 hours. The broth culture of the organisms (0.2 ml) was inoculated into 20 ml of sterile nutrient broth and incubated for 3-5 hours. The turbidity of the culture was compared with that of 0.5 Mac-Farland to standardize the culture to 10^6 cfu/ml.

Antimicrobial activity

The method described by Emeruwa (1982) was used. Briefly, 0.5 ml of the standardized culture was placed in a sterile plate so as to achieve a confluent growth. Then 18.0-20 ml of molten Nutrient agar at 45°C was added to each plate that were rocked for even spread and proper mixing of the content of the plate. The plates were allowed to solidify. Wells approximately 4 mm in diameter were bored on the surfaces of the agar medium using a sterile cork borer and the bottom of the holes were sealed or seeded with molten agar. Then 0.2 ml of the reconstituted extract at the tested concentrations was dropped into the holes while commercial standard antibiotics discs were used as positive control. The plates were allowed to stand for 30 minutes for pre-diffusion of the extract to occur and then incubated at 37°C for 24 hours and the zones of inhibition were measured to the nearest mm using transparent metre rule. The mean of triplicate results were taken.

Determination of minimum inhibitory concentrations

Bacterial strains were cultured overnight at 37°C on Nutrient broth and were adjusted to a final density of 10^6 cfu/ml. This was used to inoculate 96-well microtitre plates containing serial 5-fold dilutions of the extract (50-6.25% v/v) under aseptic conditions. The extract was dissolved in 10% dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO). The plates were incubated under aerobic condition at 37°C and examined after 24 hours. As an indication of bacterial growth, 40 μ l of 0.2 mg ml⁻¹ p-iodonitrotetrazolium solution was added to each well and incubated for 30 min at 37°C. The colourless tetrazolium salt was reduced to a red-coloured product by the biological activity of the organisms. Each treatment was performed in triplicate and complete suppression of growth at a specific concentration of extract as indicated by a clear solution was required for it to be declared active (Elof, 1998).

Determination of Minimum Bacteriocidal Concentrations

The MBC values were determined following the modified method of El-Mahmood and Doughari (2009). This was done by removing a loopful of bacterial suspension from the MIC tubes that did not show any growth and sub-cultured into Nutrient agar plates. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. After incubation, the concentration at which no visible growth was seen was recorded as the MBC.

Determination of activity index

The activity index (Arya *et al*, 2010) of the crude plant extract was calculated as

$$\text{Activity index (A.I.)} = \frac{\text{Mean of zone of inhibition of the extract}}{\text{Zone of inhibition obtained for standard antibiotic drug}}$$

The activity index of the root extract was obtained by dividing its zones of inhibition achieved by those obtained for ciprofloxacin which was the most active antibiotic.

Analysis Data

Data were presented as mean \pm S.E.M of the respective replicate. One way ANOVA was done to compare means of the groups as well as Duncan multiple range test to analyze

differences among different means using SPSS 15.0 computer software package. Differences at $P < 0.05$ were statistically significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Aloe vera has been described as one of the most famous medicinal plant in history, yet the most misunderstood in ancient times and have been used for an array of ailments (Bashir *et al.*, 2011). Numerous studies report the effectual use of this plant when functioning topically for the healing of burns, sunburns, inflammatory skin disorders and wounds (Belo *et al.*, 2006; Reider *et al.*, 2005; Paulsen *et al.*, 2005).

Percentage Yield of Extract and Phytochemical Test

One hundred and ninety-five grams of the powdered root sample yielded 17g (8.72 g) of the acetone extract. The chemical screening *Aloe vera* acetone root extract showed the presence of saponin, alkaloid, glycoside and carbohydrate (Table 1). The phytochemical screening result revealed a high presence of carbohydrates and slight presence of glycosides, alkaloids and saponins. Similar study conducted by Yebpella *et al.* (2011) reveal the presence of saponins, glycosides, flavonoids, alkaloids and tannins which conforms with results obtained in this study (Table 1).

Effect of acetone extract of the root of *A. vera* on isolated microorganisms

The result obtained for the antibacterial activity of *Aloe vera* acetone root extract is shown in Table 2. The microbial inhibitory activities of the acetone extract of the root of *A. vera* showed that the zones of inhibition increased with increase in the concentration of the extract (Table 2). Highest activity of the extract was achieved at 200 mg/ml against *Streptococcus pyogenes* which recorded a zone of inhibition of 22.00 mm in diameter while the least activity of the extract was achieved at 50 mg/ml against *Proteus mirabilis* which recorded a zone of inhibition of 5.33 mm in diameter. In comparison with study conducted by Yebpella *et al.* (2011), it was observed that methanol extract of *A. vera* when tested against *Bacillus subtilis*, *S. aureus*, *C. albicans* and *P. mirabilis* achieved zones of inhibition measuring 15mm, 18mm, 16mm and NMZI respectively while aqueous extract against the same isolates achieved zones of inhibition measuring 23 mm, 32 mm, 25 mm and 20 mm respectively. Statistically, the inhibitory activity of the acetone extract at 50 mg/ml was found to be significantly different from the other concentrations (100 and 200 mg/ml) against *S. pyogenes*. But the inhibitory potential of the extract at 200 mg/ml was observed to be significantly different from the 50 and 100 mg/ml against *P. mirabilis*. It was however generally observed that there were significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in the inhibitory activities of the extract at all tested concentrations against the isolated organisms. *A. vera* has been used as a cosmetic and medical remedy since ancient times and has gained increasing popularity in recent years (Yebpella *et al.*, 2011).

The results of the Minimum Inhibitory concentration (MIC) and Minimum Bacteriocidal concentration (MBC) of the acetone root extract *Aloe vera* against the isolated microorganisms are indicated in Table 3 and 4 respectively. An MIC of 12.5 mg/ml was achieved against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus saprophyticus*. An MIC of 6.25 mg/ml was achieved for *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus pyogenes* while an MIC of 25.0 mg/ml was achieved against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and *Proteus mirabilis* (Table 3). This result could probably be responsible for the popular use of *A. vera* gel and leaf (which had similar inhibitory activity against the same organisms) to relieve many types of gastrointestinal irritations (Foster, 1999), since *S. aureus* form part of the normal microbial flora of the skin, upper respiratory tract and intestinal tract

(Cheesbrough, 1984). Minimum Bactericidal concentration (MBC) of the *A. vera* acetone extract analyzed in this study against the various test bacterial isolates revealed varying result. An MBC of 12.5 mg/ml was achieved for *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Streptococcus pyogenes* and 50 mg/ml for *Proteus mirabilis* (Table 4) while an MIC of 25.0 mg/ml was achieved for *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *S. saprophyticus* (Table 3). It is pertinent to note that *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, an organism known usually to exhibit multidrug resistance was found to be susceptible to the root extract of *A. vera* with MIC of 25 mg/ml (Table 3).

Antibiotic susceptibility test revealed that the most active standard antibiotic was ciprofloxacin for a zone of inhibition measuring 30.0 mm against *Streptococcus pyogenes* while the least active standard antibiotics were Sparfloxacin, Gentamycin, Pefloxacin and Erythromycin which all recorded a zone of inhibition measuring 10.0 mm against *E. coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Proteus mirabilis* and *Staphylococcus aureus* respectively (Table 5). Bashir *et al.* (2011) in their study observed that the susceptibility of gram positive bacteria isolates to erythromycin, methicillin and vancomycin was generally high while that to bacitracin and novobiocin was low. This suggests that the penicillinase-resistant antibacterial agents should be selected as a first choice to treat these infections (Hoeger, 2004). The highest activity index value (1.93) of the extract was shown against gentamycin for *P. aeruginosa* while the least activity index value of 1.02 was achieved against streptomycin for *S. saprophyticus* (Table 6). This inferred that the extract was most active and most inhibitory towards *P. aeruginosa* and least active against *S. saprophyticus* following the activity index.

CONCLUSION

The present study has revealed the importance of *Aloe vera* to probably control antibiotic resistant bacteria, which have been a threat to human and animal health. Numerous plants indigenous to Africa in general have been found with amazing medicinal properties. Some are well-evaluated vis-à-vis their content of specific active principles against the target microorganism while others are not. It is therefore highly essential that studies on medicinal plants whose properties have not been fully characterized should be carried out.

Table 1: Phytochemical screening of *Aloe vera* acetone root extract

Parameter	Results
Flavonoids	-
Carbohydrates	++
Steroids	-
Glycosides	+
Terpenoids	-
Alkaloids	+
Saponins	+

Key: ++ = highly present , + = present , - = absent

Table 2: Antibacterial activity of *Aloe vera* acetone root extract

Organisms	Concentration of root extract		
	200 mg/ml	100 mg/ml	50 mg/ml
	Zone of inhibition (Mean \pm S.E.M)		
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	18.33 \pm 0.88 ^a	11.67 \pm 0.58 ^b	8.00 \pm 0.58 ^c
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	19.00 \pm 0.58 ^a	14.67 \pm 0.33 ^b	11.00 \pm 0.58 ^c
<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>	22.00 \pm 0.58 ^a	20.67 \pm 1.20 ^a	13.00 \pm 0.58 ^b
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	19.33 \pm 0.58 ^a	9.67 \pm 0.58 ^b	7.00 \pm 0.58 ^c
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	16.33 \pm 0.33 ^a	11.67 \pm 0.33 ^b	6.33 \pm 0.33 ^c
<i>Staphylococcus saprophyticus</i>	15.33 \pm 0.33 ^a	12.33 \pm 1.20 ^b	7.67 \pm 0.33 ^c
<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	12.67 \pm 0.88 ^a	8.00 \pm 0.88 ^b	5.33 \pm 0.88 ^b

The values are the mean \pm SEM of 3 replicates

Values with different alphabets within a row are significantly different at P<0.05.

Table 3: Minimum Inhibitory concentration (MIC) of *Aloe vera* acetone root extract

Organisms	50 mg/ml	25 mg/ml	12.5 mg/ml	6.25 mg/ml	3.125 mg/ml	MIC (mg/ml)
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	-	-	-	+	+	12.5
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	-	-	-	-	+	6.25
<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>	-	-	-	-	+	6.25
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	-	-	+	+	+	25.0
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	-	-	+	+	+	25.0
<i>Staphylococcus saprophyticus</i>	-	-	-	+	+	12.5
<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	-	-	+	+	+	25.0

KEY: + = Positive, - = Negative

Table 4: Minimum Bacteriocidal concentration (MBC) of *Aloe vera* acetone root extract

Organisms	50 mg/ml	25 mg/ml	12.5 mg/ml	6.25 mg/ml	3.125 mg/ml	MBC (mg/ml)
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	-	-	-	+	+	12.5
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	-	-	-	+	+	12.5
<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>	-	-	-	+	+	12.5
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	-	-	+	+	+	25.0
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	-	-	+	+	+	25.0
<i>Staphylococcus saprophyticus</i>	-	-	+	+	+	25.0
<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	-	+	+	+	+	50.0

KEY: + = Positive, - = Negative

Table 5: Zone of inhibition (mm) for antibiotics susceptibility test

Gram +ve	PEF	GN	APX	Z	AM	R	CPX	S	SXT	E
<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>	NMZI	13.0	NMZI	15.0	NMZI	NMZI	30.0	NMZI	NMZI	20.0
<i>S. saprophyticus</i>	18.0	20.0	NMZI	23.0	NMZI	NMZI	25.0	15.0	NMZI	12.0
<i>S. aureus</i>	NMZI	14.0	NMZI	20.0	NMZI	15.0	26.0	NMZI	NMZI	10.0
Gram -ve	SXT	CH	SP	CPX	AM	AU	GN	PEF	OFX	S
<i>E. coli</i>	NMZI	19.0	10.0	28.0	14.0	NMZI	10.0	13.0	23.0	NMZI
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	NMZI	NMZI	NMZI	20.0	NMZI	NMZI	15.0	14.0	21.0	NMZI
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	NMZI	NMZI	NMZI	25.0	NMZI	NMZI	10.0	NMZI	24.0	NMZI
<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	NMZI	NMZI	NMZI	22.0	NMZI	NMZI	20.0	10.0	27.0	10.0

KEY: NMZI = No Measurable Zone of Inhibition (Zone of inhibition not appreciable), PEF: Pefloxacin(30µg), GN: Gentamycin(10µg), APX: Ampiclox(30µg), Z: Zinnacef(20µg), AM: Amoxicillin(30µg), R: Rocephin(25µg), CPX: Ciprofloxacin(10µg), S: Streptomycin, SXT: Septrin(30µg), E: Erythromycin(10µg), CH: Chloranphenicol, SP: Spafloxacin, OFX: Tarivid(10µg), AU: Augmentin(30µg).

Table 6: Activity index of *Aloe vera* acetone root extract against commercial antibiotic

Organisms	PEF	GN	AM	CPX	APX	Z	R	S	SXT	E	CH	SP	AU	OFX
<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>	NZ	1.69	NZ	0.73	NZ	1.47	NZ	NZ	NZ	1.10	NA	NA	NA	NA
<i>S. saprophyticus</i>	0.85	0.77	NZ	0.61	NZ	0.67	NZ	1.02	NZ	1.27	NA	NA	NA	NA
<i>S. aureus</i>	NZ	1.36	NZ	0.73	NZ	0.95	1.27	NZ	NZ	1.90	NA	NA	NA	NA
<i>E. coli</i>	1.41	1.83	1.31	0.65	NA	NA	NA	NZ	NZ	NA	0.96	1.83	NZ	0.80
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	1.17	1.09	NZ	0.82	NA	NA	NA	NZ	NZ	NA	NZ	NZ	NZ	0.78
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	NZ	1.93	NZ	0.77	NA	NA	NA	NZ	NZ	NA	NZ	NZ	NZ	0.81
<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	1.27	0.63	NZ	0.58	NA	NA	NA	1.27	NZ	NA	NZ	NZ	NZ	0.47

KEY: NZ = No zone shown by the isolate against the antibiotics, NA: Not Applicable, PEF: Pefloxacin(30µg), GN:Gentamycin(10µg), APX: Ampiclox(30µg), Z: Zinnacef(20µg), AM: Amoxicillin(30µg), R: Rocephin(25µg), CPX: Ciprofloxacin(10µg),S: Streptomycin, SXT: Septrin(30µg), E: Erythromycin(10µg), CH: Chloramphenicol, SP: Sparfloxacin, OFX: Tarivid(10µg), AU: Augmentin(30µg).

NB: Activity index ≥ 1.0 are considered significant

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